

CUSTOMER'S PERCEPTIONS TOWARDS DIGITAL ADVERTISEMENTS

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Abstract:

Now a day, Internet has become a major source for Advertisements to attract the customers. The internet may affect their purchase decision depending upon the advertisements. Different Customers have different attitudes towards internet advertisements. Customer's perception may be defined as Emotional Feelings, Beliefs, and Behaviours about Product, Services, Companies and Institutions. Digital Advertisements may be defined as a Promotional Tool that uses Internet and WWW to deliver their messages to attract and retain the Customers. It gives the opportunity to the marketers to target their customized Customers. Internet advertisements can create a good or bad impression on the Consumers. So this research paper represents the perception of customers relating to the digital advertisements.

Key Words: Internet, Advertisements, Promotional Tool, Emotional Feelings, Beliefs, and Behaviours and www.

Introduction:

Now a day, internet has become a major source for advertisements. Everyone can access to the internet which may affect their purchase decision depending upon the advertisements. Different Customers have different attitudes towards internet advertisements. The internet was designed in early 1950's. It was used by different scientists, engineers and experts for some specific purposes. Afterwards, people used it for the communication and to share information through E-mails. Now it is an important source for advertisements to attract customers. Customer's perception may be defined as emotional feelings, beliefs, and behaviours about Product, services, companies and institutions. Digital advertisements may be defined as a promotional tool that uses internet and WORLD WIDE WEB to deliver their messages to attract and retain the Customers. It gives the opportunity to the marketers to target their customized Customers. Internet advertisements can create a good or bad impression on the Consumers. The ultimate aim of every manufacturer is to attract the Customer through advertisements. Thus it is necessary to know the perception and behaviour of customers towards digital advertisements. Without knowing them, a marketer cannot attain success.

Objective of the Study:

- ✓ To study the socio, economic and demographic status of the respondents in the study area.
- ✓ To find out the factors which influenced to make their purchase decision
- ✓ To find out the satisfaction level of the customers towards the selected Web sites.
- ✓ To offer the suggestion based on the findings of the study.

Methodology:

The researcher has undertaken an Analytical Study. Perception of customers towards Digital advertisements has been analyzed.

Sources of Data:

- ✓ The data required for the study are collected through primary and secondary sources.
- ✓ **Primary Data:** The Primary data have been collected by preparing questionnaires schedule. The data have been collected directly from the internet users in Sivakasi.
- ✓ **Secondary Data:** The secondary sources needed for the study have been collected from various Books, Journals and Magazines, related research report and search engine.

Sampling Design:

The primary data have been gathered by the researcher from the various categories of the customers. As the numbers of internet users are infinite, it is very difficult to adopt the census method to collect data. So the researcher has used convenience sampling. A sample of 100 respondents of using internet has been selected using convenient sampling method.

Statistical Tools:

- ✓ The researcher has used the following statistical tools for the statistical interpretation of data.
- ✓ Percentage analysis
- ✓ Weighed Arithmetic mean

- ✓ Chi-Square Test
- ✓ Man Whitney Rank Sum U – Test

Hypothesis of the Study:

The following hypotheses have been framed for the study.

- ✓ There is no relationship between gender of the respondents and amount spent to internet per month.
- ✓ There is no relationship between monthly income of the respondents and amount spent to internet per month.
- ✓ There is no relationship between gender of the respondents and satisfaction level.

Results and Discussion:

Table 1.1: Socio Economic Profile of the respondents

S.No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage
Gender Wise Classification of Respondents			
1	Male	63	63.00
2	Female	37	37.00
Age Wise Classification of Respondents			
1	Below 21 years	20	20.00
2	21 years to 30 years	73	73.00
3	31 years to 40 years	5	5.00
4	41 years 50 years	2	2.00
Level of Education			
1	Below SSLC	2	2.00
2	HSC school	6	6.00
3	UG level	25	25.00
4	PG level	59	59.00
5	Diploma	4	4.00
6	Doctorate	4	4.00
Marital Status			
1	Married	21	21.00
2	Unmarried	79	79.00
Occupation of the Respondents			
1	Business man	7	27.00
2	Profession	6	23.00
3	Govt employee	7	27.00
4	Private employee	5	19.00
5	Pensioner	4	4.00
Monthly Family Income of Respondents			
1	Below to Rs.10000	37	37.00
2	Rs.10001 to Rs.15000	30	30.00
3	Rs.15001 to Rs.20000	20	20.00
4	Rs.20001 to Rs.25000	8	8.00
5	Rs.25000 and above	5	5.00

Source: Primary Data

The above table 1.1 represents that, out of 100 respondents, 63 respondents are Male, 73 respondents are belongs to 21-30 years, 59 respondents are having PG level educational qualification, 79 respondents are unmarried, 7 respondents are Government employees and 7 respondents are Businessman and 37 respondents are earned above Rs.10000 income.

Customer Opinion about Factors Influenced to Purchase:

In this survey the customers have been asked to provide their view concerning the elements determining the factors influenced. The views are held for 9 statements which are associated to the elements determining the factors influenced to purchase by acquiring scaling technique, Likert five point scale Table 1.2 Shows that the opinion of customers about the factors influenced to purchase.

Table 1.3: Custom ER Opinion about Influencing Factor

S.No	Particular	H.S	S	N	D.S	S.D	Total	WAM	RANK
1	Product and service can be browsed at any time	245	128	96	32	3	504	5.04	I
2	24hours/7days a week	165	192	48	4	1	410	4.1	II
3	Variety of feature	176	148	69	12	0	405	4.05	III
4	Prices can be compared	110	176	84	12	0	312	3.82	IX
5	Features can be compared	125	152	66	22	6	371	3.71	VI

6	Quick feedback of the Customer	110	160	87	10	1	368	3.68	VII
7	Customer privacy Policy	110	156	75	18	5	364	3.64	VIII
8	Multiple choices	120	180	63	10	5	378	3.78	IV
9	Can be checked and browsed repeatedly	145	120	90	16	3	374	3.74	V

Source: Primary Data

By giving ranking proposal, the features “Products and services can be browsed at any time” got first rank, “24hours/7days a week access” got second rank, “Variety of features” got third rank, “Multiple choices” got fourth rank, “Can be checked privacy policy” got fifth rank, “Features can be compared” got sixth rank, “Features can be compared” got seventh rank, “Customer privacy policy” got eighth rank, “ prices can be compared” got ninth rank.

Result of Hypothesis:

Hypothesis 1: There is no relationship between gender of the respondents and amount spent to internet per month”.

To test the above hypothesis, chi-square test has been applied by using SPSS and the result is presented in the following Table 1.4.

Chi-Square Tests:

Pearson Chi-Square	1 .097 ^a	4	.895
Likelihood Ratio	1.427	4	.840
Linear-by-Linear	.119	1	.730
Association N of Valid Cases	100		

- ✓ 4 cells (40.0%) have expected count less than 5.
- ✓ The minimum expected count is .37.

Result:

From Table 3.20 it is found that the p-value (0.895) is more than the table value of 0.05 (1.097) at 5 per cent level. Hence null hypothesis is accepted. So it is concluded that there is no relationship between the Gender of the respondents and Amount spent to internet per month.

Hypothesis 2: “There is no relationship between gender of the respondents and overall satisfaction”.

To test the above hypothesis, Man Whitney Rank sum U-Test has been applied by using SPSS and the result is presented in the following Table 3.22.

Table 3.22: Gender of the Respondents and Overall Satisfaction

Gender		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Level of Satisfaction	Male	63	49.74	3133.50
	Female	37	51.80	1916.50
Total		100		

Source: Computed Data

Test Statistics:

	Level of Satisfaction
Mann-Whitney U	1117.500
Wilcoxon W	3 133.500
Z	-.390
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.697

From Table 3.22 it is found that the p-value (.697) is more than the table value of 0.05 at 5 per cent level. Hence null hypothesis is accepted. So it is concluded that there is no relationship between gender of the respondents and overall satisfaction.

Findings of the Study:

- ✓ It is understood from the survey that majority of the respondents (67.00 percent) are male.
- ✓ It is noted that majority of the respondents (73.00 percent) are belonging to the age group of 21years to 30 years.
- ✓ It is found that majority of the respondents (79.00 percent) are unmarried.
- ✓ It is inferred that most of the respondents (59.00 percent) up to Post Graduate level.
- ✓ It is evident that most of the respondents (27.00 percent) are Businessman and Govt employees.
- ✓ It is evident that the most of the respondents (37.00 percent) are earning monthly income up to below Rs.10000.
- ✓ There is no relationship between the Gender of the respondents and Amount spent to internet per month.
- ✓ There is no relationship between gender of the respondents and overall satisfaction.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Customers should be educated on online advertisement procedure with proper steps to be followed while online shopping.

- ✓ Online advertisement websites should be made more attractive and appealing to the customers in order to retain the potential customers.
- ✓ Customers disputes to be monitored by online customers support and should be responded and resolved frequently.
- ✓ By creating an online advertising with the criteria of informative, hedonic and materialism, the attractiveness of the advertising will increase, this would influence consumers to hold a more favourable towards the advertising and in turn increase their awareness on the advertised products and services.
- ✓ It is suggested that the customers should follow all the security tips and instruction given by the company before the placement of their order.

Conclusion:

Special attentions to internet advertisements are of high importance for considering customer needs and personalizing sent advertisement messages. Thus, advertisers can create positive attitudes in the consumers by providing rich content of the information in sent advertisements and trustable atmosphere in internet. In formativeness, Entertainment, and correct usage of interaction and credibility can lead to the proper perceptions in internet consumers. Enough and correct information about more complicated products along with attractive posters and step-by- step instructions encourage consumers to buy or visit the site.

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